

DOMESTIC INVESTMENT GROWTH RESPONSE TO LENDING RATE IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The research work borders around growth response of total domestic investment to lending rates in Nigeria, spanning 1981 through 2023. Precisely, the study determines the adjustment timeline and impact of lending rates on total domestic investment, while incorporating other variables such as inflation, exchange rates, and public and private sector credits. Annual data on the variables were culled from publications of Central Bank of Nigeria bulletins. The study applied Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root tests (resulting in mixed of I(0) and I(1) level series), ARDL bounds testing for long-run association and Error Correction Modeling (ECM) with optimal lag 1. The analysis was supplemented by Koyck median lag analysis. The study found a negative but marginally insignificant lagged lending rate effect on domestic investment. However, past investment significantly boosts current investment levels by 42%. The ECT shows 3.4% annual disequilibrium adjustment, with half the effect being realized in 1.91 years and complete adjustment realizable in approximately 4 years. A mild positive inflationary effect on investment is reported, while exchange rates and credits showed insignificant effects. The study concluded that high lending rates have a dampening effect on domestic investment growth with delayed transmission. Among others, it was recommended that mild lending rates and targeted macro-prudential tools for real sectors growth should be the concern of the government, to accelerate adjustment and foster sustained investment-led growth.

Keywords: Lending Rate, Domestic Investment, Growth response, ECT, Koyck, Adjustment.

JEL Code: E22, E43, E51, E52, O10

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most contentious policies of the monetary authority borders around the rate of interest, which incidentally houses the lending rate. This is because it changes in reaction to several economic factors, including shifts in federal policy, crises in the local and global financial markets and changes in the outlook of long-term economic growth, the business climate, inflation, and investment (Osuji, 2020). Interest rate is what it costs to borrow funds. It is a macroeconomic technique for demand management. Thus, it is widely acknowledged as the main factor that influences investment. Every country uses interest rates, especially the lending rate, essentially as a tool for monetary policy to enhance output and infrastructure growth, in relation to investment. A noticeable aspect is the short-term and long-term fluctuations in rate of interest. Its variations influence saving and investing decisions directly or indirectly (George-Anokwuru, 2017). Investments that are funded through stocks and bonds are often liable to the risk of limited consumption when returns on owning these assets are extremely variable. Thus, interest rate policy is one of the core challenges that confront Nigeria due to its critical function in the promotion of savings which are needed for investment purposes (Abdullahi, 2022).

Given the way it balances up supply and demand in the financial sector, understanding the influence of lending rates on locally made investment, is germane when formulating policies to support national growth. Banks operate as intermediaries by accepting deposits and channeling it towards investors in the form of loans and advances (Abdullahi, 2022). Interest rate is therefore the means through which funds are moved from savers to borrowers via variety of financial intermediaries, including government securities, mutual funds, insurance companies and capital markets. The availability of investible funds is essential for all economic investments, which ultimately result in economic growth and progress (Patrick & Andabai, 2024). Thus, the degree to which this is possible depends on the interest or lending rate, the financial sector development, and people's saving and investing habits. The changes in interest rate greatly influence investment activity and, consequently, a country's economic growth. In most cases, economic growth depends on the amount of investment, whereas the volume of investment depends on interest rate paid by investors to obtain funds from the financial market. Investment tends to increase as the prime lending interest rate reduces, and vice versa (George-Anokwuru, 2017). Generally, interest rates include loan rates, deposit rates, interbank rates, Treasury bill rates, and minimum rediscount rates (Davis and Emerenini, 2015). Consequently, the amount of funds made available by lenders as credits to finance investment is determined by the banks' deposit volume, which includes both savings and demand deposits. Increasing the credit provided by the banks because of the current lending rate is a major force that drives economic growth (Aliyu and Yusuf, 2013).

Economists believe in the existence of inverse interaction between rate of interest and the growth of investment. The cost of borrowing increases with interest rates, and when there is a surge in borrowing costs, businesses are likely to borrow less. In this sense, as interest rates rise, investment declines. However, lower lending interest rates make borrowing more affordable and increase the likelihood that businesses will invest (George-Anokwuru, 2017). This influences economic agents' choices on investments and savings. As a result, interest rates are typically thought of as a key monetary policy instrument. Therefore, any time the interest rate structure is altered, the relative interest rates that arise will cause changes in the public and bank market portfolios. The pattern of spending and savings businesses and individuals can be used to illustrate the crucial impact interest rates play in an economy (Inimino *et al.*, 2018). It is noteworthy that Nigeria's interest rate policies have traditionally been unpredictable due to changing government policies, crises in the local and global financial markets, and changes in

the expectation for inflation and long-term economic development (Abdullahi, 2022). Currently, the situation of interest rate in the economy is worrisome. This is evident in the recent upward trends of interest rate. It jumped from 14 percent in 2022 to 18.75 percent in 2023 and subsequently rose to 27.5 percent in 2024. Similarly, the prime lending rate moved from 13.85 percent in 2022 to 14.01 percent in 2023, and closes at 18.56 percent in 2024 (Tokede, 2025). Despite the country's efforts to liberalize its domestic financial market and enact interest rate policies that encourages investment, optimal lending rate is yet a task to overcome (Inimino *et al.*, 2018).

Local investment, in both short and long terms, have been largely influenced by bank lending rate in Nigeria (Kwode, 2024; Eze and Eze, 2023; Shittu, Olorunfemi and Adejola, 2023). However, the extent to which lending rates in the close and distant past currently influences growth of investment in the country has never been considered in past studies. This is inclusive of works done in other West African countries. In Ghana, the work of Solomon and Kofi (2020) never had a conclusive finding as it only showed that interest rate and domestic investment exhibit both long-term and short-term relationship. The work of Willy and Agnes (2020) related lending rate with total investment in Kenya. This obscured the performance of domestic investment given the lending rate.

In one part, this study differ from the past works by concerning itself with domestic investment and taking into account the effect of past and current domestic investment and lending rate on the behavior of domestic investment in the current period. In a bid to mitigate the progressively deteriorating economy and rising inflation, which was around 23.71% in April 2025, the apex bank raised the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) to 27.5% leading to a pullback by local investors from accessing loans (CBN, 2025). The resultant outcry also prompted the renewed interest on this subject matter.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Interest rates are generally classified as the policy rate, deposit rate or lending rates. The policy rate is the rate that apex banks use to evaluate the cost, quantity and circulating money within the country to accomplish specific growth objectives. As regards deposit rates, financial institutions pay interest on savings and time deposits with varying maturities, including one-month and fixed deposits. However, lending rates are the interest that moneylenders, banks, and other institutions charge borrowers to meet their short- and medium-term financial needs. The term "lending rate" also refer to the rate that banks charge their clients on loans that are made available to them. Lending rates represents the rental payments made by borrowers when they use credit and the return that lenders receive over time for parting with their money (Gbosi, 2005). This means that it is the amount that a lender charges a borrower for using borrowed funds, denoted as a percentage of the principal (CBN, 2016). Lending rate is a proportion of the actual capital lent out overtime; say a year, a month, a week, or a day. It is a proportion or percentage of the principal paid as a fee over a predetermined period (Inimino *et al.*, 2018). Given the way it works that interest rate is lower when the loan is more, monthly or annual payment due therefore becomes minimal. This reduces the proportion of a consumer's income used to service debt, thus, lesser payments will free up more funds for purchases. However, when the rate at which money is lent out is high it could take more funds from borrower to the lender. With respect to capital inflows and outflows, a relative high interest rate in comparison to other countries attract foreign capital because of the potential returns to foreign investors, and vice versa (Inimino *et al.*, 2018).

In Nigeria, lending rate is sub-divided into maximum and prime lending rates. While the prime rate is charged by banks on their creditworthy clients, majorly the incorporated organizations, a maximum lending rate is the rate charge the customers with poor credit scores. The Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) entails the rate at which the apex banks lend to banks in the course of their responsibilities as lenders of last resort. In other words, it is the interest rate that deposit money banks pay the central bank of a country when they borrow money (Acha, 2011; Inimino *et al.*, 2018). Although the banks will be deterred from borrowing from the central bank by a high MPR, a low MPR will promote borrowing. Thus, the MPR serves as a benchmark for all other market interest rates and is supposed to convey the position of monetary policy. Interest rate deregulation in Nigeria has provided a fair playing ground for the market to set interest rates in the country such that market forces for loanable funds determine interest rates for bank deposits and lending when interest rates are deregulated, (Davis and Emereni, 2015). When interest rates drops, therefore, there are tendencies for domestic investment to rise (CBN, 2019; World Bank, 2020).

Domestic investment focuses on the purchase of assets in order to forgo current spending in favour of future wealth generation (Mogaji, Folade & Ogundipe, 2020). Domestic investment is practically engaged in by the regional financial innovators and investors. This form of investment has the benefit of discouraging capital flight to other countries. Nigeria's effort towards supporting domestic investment to raise standards of living, productivity, employment creation, creativity, and poverty reduction has increased (Ayeni 2004). Domestic investments have multiplier effects on national income and thus, are a driver to growth and development, increased income and demand, aggregate employment and production (Mogaji *et al.*, 2020). Thus, balancing the interplay between interest rates, in the form of lending rate, and domestic investment is frequently visited by nations that are inclined to growth and development.

2.1 Theoretical Review

The Keynesian theory, (1936), Adam Smiths, (1776) and the Duesenberry theory, (1949), which serves as the theoretical foundation for this research, attended to linkage that connects interest rate and investment. According to classical theorists, interest rates were seen as factors that influence the interaction between capital supply and demand. The theory states that when people delay their current purchases to earn higher interest rate on their capital, the supply side of the capital would witness increase in interest rates, which may lead to insufficient cash to be ploughed into promising investments (Smiths, 1776). It is believed that demand for borrowed fund drops when rate of interest is high. The neo-classical school challenged the belief that income a permanent influence in the model. They rather opined that income is actually a variable rather than constant as the classical school suggested (Keynes, 1936). The classical hypothesis was also criticized for failing to acknowledge how investment affects the country's income. While the time preference dictates the amount of capital supplied in the economy, the demand for capital is a function of the estimated capital's output (Onuchuku *et al.*, 2018). Keynes believed that there are main reasons for retaining money, including transactional, precautionary and speculative. The speculative incentive is more closely associated with money demand, while rate of interest has a functional relationship with money volume. Consequently, market process determines the level of interest rate. The first two of the Keynes' three recognized motives of money retention are income-reliant, while the last is interest rate-reliant. Combining the transactional, speculative, and precautionary reasons for money holdings yields the total money demand. The speculative motive, which hinges on movement in the rate of

interest, explains the desire for idle balances, whilst the other two motives explain the need for readily available money balances.

Theory of financial investment postulated interest rate as a cost of borrowing money. In the meantime, the rate of interest is constant regardless of the amount of investment made (Duesenberry, 1949). Investors can access limitless financial resources at the going rate of interest in the market as long as payback is guaranteed. This indicates that producers have a perfectly elastic supply of financial resources. However, in reality, the unfettered vision of always allocating resources to producers at a fixed rate of interest is not accurate. This is because as required fund by investors increase, interest rates on capital rise as well. Thus, investors must obtain funds from the market at the going rate of interest in order to get the necessary funds for investment expenditures (Adenuga, 2020). From another perspective, Duesenberry, (1949) combined the theories of profit and investment acceleration. Flow of cash in the economy was recognized by the theory as a major factor influencing investment. The ratio of capital to income determines the growth rates of both income and capital stock, and while income increases, savings fall short of investment. Thus, investment is seen as being dependent on stock of fund, income, profit, and the lending rate that determines what is paid back to the lender.

2.2 Empirical Review

Various researchers on the connection between interest rate, particularly, lending rate and domestic investment have empirically conducted several studies, locally and internationally. Apere and Akarara (2024) worked on interest rate – investment nexus in Nigeria between 1981 and 2022 using multivariate co-integration and ECM techniques. Findings showed that capital formation and the interest rate proxies exhibited long association. Finding from ECM further showed that rate of interest negatively influence investment, and about 40% disequilibrium in the preceding year would be catered for in the succeeding year. It was therefore concluded that investment could be discouraged by high rate of interest in Nigeria.

Kwode (2024) sampled key macroeconomic variables, including lending rate and analyzed their impact on domestic investment in Nigeria using OLS technique over the period of 29 years, (1991 through 2020). The finding showed that long period of relationship exists between the sampled macroeconomic indicators (such as lending rates, inflation, domestic savings, money supply, and real GDP) and the domestic investment in Nigeria as revealed by the co-integration results. The OLS results also exhibited significantly positive connection among local savings, supply of money, real GDP and local investment. However, a significant and negative association exists between prime lending rate, inflation rate and local investment. Hence, it was suggested that government should implement effective fiscal and monetary policies to tackle inflation and macroeconomic variables.

Eze and Eze (2023) in their work covering 1986 through 2019 analyzed how domestic investment responded to the rate of interest charged in the country, using ARDL model and co-integration analysis. The research discovered that rate of interest significantly but negatively affected domestic investment overtime. Interest rate was also discovered to exhibit multiple breaks within 3 years, that is, 2002, 2009 and 2014. It was suggested that the monetary authority needed to promote local investment in the country through lower interest rate utilization.

Nwamuo and Agu (2022) studied the influence of rate of interest on growth of investment employing annual time series of 38 years (1981-2019), obtained from the CBN. The study

adopted the ECM regression. Money supply, rate of interest and inflation positively influence growth of investment. Interest rate was also discovered to positively affect investment. The study recommended that the government needed to bring up sustainable monetary policies that enhance interest rate that will boost investment. This was suggested to be done through the monetary authority.

Mogaji *et al* (2020) examined the existing connection among interest rate, inflation and local investors in Nigeria using ARDL techniques using a sample period of 1986 through 2018. The findings showed that the preceding year's stable rate of inflation caused an upsurge in domestic investment. However, public spending and interest rate were discovered to reduce investment. It was therefore, suggested that stable inflation rate with reduced interest rate will boost domestic investments in Nigeria.

Thuy, Anh, and Diem (2020) used GMM to assess how Vietnam's monetary policy affected local investment. Findings showed that domestic credit, low rate of interest and supply of money have large and beneficial influence on domestic investment. The Vietnam government was recommended to encourage continued growth in domestic investment by maintaining low interest rate while ensuring increased money supply.

In Jordan, Majed and Ahmad (2020) used the co-integration test and vector autoregressive regression to analyze how interest rates influenced domestic investment between 1990 and 2005. While income was found to positively influence investment, rate of interest hampered its growth. Suggestion was that lower lending rate that will encourage local investors should be explored in the country. Solomon and Kofi (2020) analyzed the impact of interest rate on private investment over the period of 1986 to 2016 in Ghana using ARDL model. Result revealed an enduring connection between interest rate and domestic investment. Amanu (2020) examined factors influencing local investment in Ethiopia using the OLS technique, covering the period between 1975 and 2009. Findings revealed that credits and real GDP positively and significantly influenced domestic investments. On the contrary, public investment, inflation rate and lending rate negatively influenced local investment of Ethiopia. The study recommended monetary policies towards lowering lending rate to enhance investment growth.

The research conducted in Kenya by Monica, Willy and Agnes (2020) used vector autoregressive technique to analyze the influence of interest rates on the growth of domestic investment. Just like Amanu (2020) and a host of the reviewed studies, lending rate was discovered to significantly impair on investment growth in the country.

Ijirshar, Anjande, Fefa and Mile (2019) fitted a dynamic regression to determine stages of investment growth and the impact on investment across 47 countries in Africa. Growth of investment in Nigeria and other African nations was discovered to be positive. Government of African nations were implored to implement policies that encourages domestic savings, which will make funds available for investment, while considering foreign direct investment as a supplement to growth factors. Inimino, Abuo and Bosco (2018) studied the influence of interest rate on domestic private investment in Nigeria from 1980 through 2015. A bound testing was used to examine the long-term association among adopted variables while ARDL regression was also fitted. The long-run test confirmed existence of cointegration. The study also found that monetary policy negatively affects domestic private investment, while lending rate positively influences private investment. The study established that output level in the country

negatively affected domestic investment. The authorities needed to promote friendly lending rate that will encourage local investors to channel their resources into investment.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

The research work draws on the Keynesian theory (1936), classical theory (Smith, 1776) and Duesenberry's (1949) theory of investment in examining how lending rates affect domestic investment growth in the Nigerian context. This is justified by the existing inter-link among these theories on the study subject matter. Keynesian theory emphasizes the role of interest rates' in liquidity preference, in a situation where lower rates reduce speculative money holdings while encouraging investment through precautionary and transactional motives. This links the nation's monetary policy to its various economic activities. The classical theory asserts that interest rates ensure the balancing of capital supply and demand, where high rates cause savings to rise but discourage borrowing, thus stifling investment. Duesenberry's theory incorporates return acceleration with cash flows. Interest rate is viewed as cost of borrowing that rise with demand but has the tendency to constrain investment if income growth is low. Collectively these theories form the basis upon which the research question is framed. An inverse relationship is hypothesized between lending rates and domestic investment, given that increased rates raise capital costs, reduce borrowing and impede growth, while previous investments and income strengthen expansionary effects.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Type and Source of Data

The research made use of annual time series extracted from various published CBN reports and bulletin. Adopted series in the research work are total domestic investment, inflation, lending rate, exchange rate and public and private sector credits. Study variables were chosen based on their macroeconomic relevance to investment dynamics, and as supported by prior studies (Nwamuo and Agu, 2022; Kwode, 2024). Lending rate was selected as the primary interest variable due to its significance in borrowing costs. While inflation and exchange rates capture price and currency stability effects, public and private sector credits reflects credit availability for investment funding.

3.2 Method of Analysis

Descriptive analysis of the data set was carried out after which the trends were examined. The series were thereafter checked to ascertain the presence of random walk or otherwise, using the ADF revealing mixed integration orders $I(0)$ and $I(1)$. This prompts the ARDL bounds testing which confirmed existence of long-run relationship. The study selected optimum lag length using Akaike (AIC), Schwarz (SC), and Hannan-Quinn (HQ) criteria. All the criteria suggested an optimal lag of 1 to ensure a parsimonious ECM for short-run dynamics and adjustment speed. The study also checked for the rate of adjustment of variables to equilibrium. It also ascertained required time for both the half and total effect of change in total domestic investment to be realized when lending rate and other variables, changed. This was done using the Koyck median lag (Gujarati, 2004)

The Koyck model used in estimating the adjustment period in this study captures the delayed and decaying effects of changes in lending rates and other variables on domestic investment over time. The model thus provides a practical timeline or frame for policy realization. This aligns with dynamic economic responses where previous values are known to influence current outcomes.

3.3 Model Specification

The method of analysis used in this study follows Nwamuo and Agu, (2022) where the impact of interest rate on investment was examined. The functional form of the model is as below

$$Total\ Domestic\ Investment = f(Lending\ rate) \tag{1}$$

When all variables of interest are incorporated into equation 1, the model becomes

$$TDI = f(LEND_R, INFR, EXCHR, PPSC) \tag{2}$$

When equation 2 above is explicitly specified, it takes the form

$$TDI_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LEND_R + \beta_2 INFR + \beta_3 EXCHR + \beta_4 PPSC + U_t \tag{3}$$

Where; *TDI* = Total Domestic Investment (N'billion), *LEND_R* = Lending rate (Percentage), *INFR* = Inflation rate (Percentage), *EXCHR* = Exchange rate (Naira/\$), *PPSC* = Public and Private sector credits (Percentage of GDP), $\beta_0 - \beta_4$ = Coefficient of inflation rate, U_t = Error term, $t = 1981-2023$.

4 RESULTS PRESENTATION

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

The statistics describing lending rate and other variables of interest are presented and discussed below

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis

Variable	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	J-B Prob	Obs.
TDI	11032.1	3078.8	82889	87.145	18618	0.00	43
LEND_R	22.595	22.508	36.090	10.000	6.0551	0.69	43
INFR	19.079	13.007	72.836	5.3880	16.281	0.00	43
EXCHR	128.05	118.56	645.20	0.6100	142.74	0.00	43
PPSC	9.5809	8.2489	19.626	4.9575	3.5877	0.06	43

Source: Authors' computation, 2025

On the average, total domestic investment, lending rate, inflation rate, exchange rate, and public and private sector credits are N11billion, 22.5%, 19.%, N128 to a Dollar, and 9.58% of GDP respectively. Total domestic investment however deviated from the mean at 18,618.60, while lending rate deviated by 6.05 from its mean. The descriptive analysis showed that total domestic investment, lending rate and exchange rate, are not normally distributed since their Jarque-Bera probabilities are less than 0.05. However, public and private sector credit and interest rate, are normally distributed with higher probability values.

4.2 Trend of Variables

Figure 1: Graphs showing trend of variables

Source: Authors' compilation, 2025

As shown in the first panel of the figure above, total domestic investment in the country was low for almost two decades. This could be attributed to high lending rate (interest rate) experienced in the country at that point in time, as revealed in the interest rate panel. The low domestic investment caused by high lending rates which translates to high cost of capital, discourages investors from accessing public funds. This is in consonance with the establishment of Shittu *et al*, (2023). The resultant effect is reduced output and income. The rate of inflation in the country, as depicted, was undulating with sharp increases and falls from the beginning of the study period until around year 2000. The indication here is that the low total domestic investment caused by high lending rate led to low output level in the country, as such forcing general price level to rise. Although the rate of inflation later dropped significantly in the later years. The rate at which domestic Naira exchanges for dollar was relatively lower

from 1981 through the early 2000, compared with the later part of the study period. While the rate at which the Naira depreciates was mild between year 2000 and 2005, it experienced rapid depreciation in the last 20 years of the period of study. Public and Private credits as a percentage of GDP was relatively lower in comparison with the later part of the study. This, again, explained why investment was low during the earlier part of the study with the succeeding ripple effects on other key macroeconomic variables in the country, such as output and general price level.

4.3 Inferential Analysis

4.3.1 Unit Root Test

Variables were tested for random walk by the ADF to determine their levels of stationarity. The null hypothesis of the test posits that there is presence of random walk in each of the variables. The alternative hypothesis suggested that the problem is not inherent in them.

Table 2: Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit root Test Result

Variable	ADF Stat @ level	ADF Stat @ 1 st Diff	Order of Integration
LogTDI	0.7133 (0.9911)	-4.2671 (0.0016)	I(1)
LEND_R	-2.9339 (0.0499)	-	I(0)
INFR	-3.0824 (0.0356)	-	I(0)
EXCHR	-1.9603 (0.3024)	-5.4968 (0.0000)	I(1)
PPSC	-2.1046 (0.2440)	-6.0606 (0.0000)	I(1)

Source: Authors' computation, 2025.

The result table, presented above, indicated that total domestic investment, exchange rate and public and private sector credit are integrated after first difference, that is, they are stationary at level I(1). Lending and inflation rates are integrated at level. This means the two variables are I(0) variables.

4.3.2 Bound Testing

The existence of I(1) variables necessitated the examination for long-term association, hence the usage of bound testing approach to check for linear association or otherwise, among the series. The result and discussion are presented below.

Table 3: ARDL Bounds Test Results

<i>Test Stat</i>	<i>Value</i>	<i>k</i>
<i>F-statistics</i>	5.295019	4

Critical Value Bounds		
<i>Significance</i>	<i>I₀ Bound</i>	<i>I₁ Bound</i>
10%	2.45	3.52
5%	2.86	4.01
1%	3.74	5.06

Source: Authors' computation, 2025

The study rejects the null hypothesis of non-existence of linear association because the F-statistic of 5.295019 is above the critical value at the upper bound (I₁) at 5%. This establishes the presence of long run relationship between total domestic investment and some of the explanatory variables.

4.3.3 Optimum Lag Selection

The table below presents result of the lag-length adoption criteria conducted in the study analysis.

Table 4: Lag Length selection Result

Lag	AIC	SC	HQ
0	2.5952	2.8085	2.6717
1	33.816*	-1.1706*	-1.3347*
2	-1.3752	-1.0766	-1.2681
3	-1.3348	-0.9936	-1.2124
4	-1.3359	-0.9520	-1.1981

**Indicates lag order selected by the criterion; AIC = Akaike information criterion; SC = Schwarz information criterion; HQ = Hannan-Quinn information criterion*

Source: Authors' computation, 2025

Optimum lag-length selection test was conducted to ensure that the ECM regression used in the study, is correctly fitted. The lag-length result, as suggested by the Schwarz information criterion (SC), Akaike information criterion (AIC), and Hannan-Quinn information criterion (HQ), indicates lag order 1 as the optimum lag best to carry out the ECM regression.

4.3.4 Error Correction Model (ECM) Regression

The detected association among the series necessitated the fitted ECM, which helped in determining the speed of adjustment that is required for convergence. The result table and discussion are below.

Table 5: ECM Regression Results

<i>Dependent Variable: Log TDI</i>			
<i>Variable</i>	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>P-value</i>
<i>C</i>	0.090554	0.032979	0.0096
<i>D(LogTDI(-1))</i>	0.422421	0.148203	0.0074
<i>D(LEND_R(-1))</i>	-0.010185	0.005383	0.0670
<i>D(INFR(-1))</i>	0.002908	0.001477	0.0472
<i>D(EXCHR(-1))</i>	0.000917	0.001131	0.4231
<i>D(PPSC(-1))</i>	-0.003483	0.011241	0.7586
<i>ECT(-1)</i>	-0.304141	0.032123	0.0254
<i>R²</i>	0.321362		
<i>Adjusted R²</i>	0.201602		
<i>Prob (F-stat)</i>	0.030581		
<i>Durbin Watson</i>	2.167479		

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025.

From the ECM result above, coefficient of one period lag of total domestic investment is 0.422421, indicating that a rise in total domestic investment in the immediate past year will cause its current value to increase by 42%. This impact of increase is established to be significant at 1%. The coefficient of a period lag of lending rate, which is -0.010185, indicates that the previous year's lending rate negatively affect total domestic investment. However, the adverse effect of previous year's lending rate on total domestic investment is not significant. Iheonu and Nwakeze, (2016) also found the same relationship. The coefficient of the lag of rate of inflation, 0.0029808, indicated that a rise in rate of inflation in the previous year caused total domestic investment in the current year to slightly, rise by 0.3%. The probability value of 0.0472 implies that effect of the increase in previous level of inflation rate on total domestic investment is statistically significant at 5%. Estimate of the immediate past year exchange rate of 0.000917 denotes that its increase influenced total domestic investment to rise by a meagre 0.092%. The effect is insignificant. The error correction term ECT(-1) value, representing speed of adjustment, is -0.304141, indicating that about 3.4% of disequilibrium encountered by Nigeria's domestic investment caused by other variables, during the period, is corrected for in each year. However, the coefficient of the constant of 0.090554 shows that total domestic investment in Nigeria will still be as much as 9.1% when all adopted independent variables in the study are zero. This indicates that total domestic investment tends to be influenced by other variables outside the scope of the study.

To examine how much time it requires for the first half or 50% of total change in domestic investment to respond to changes in the adopted independent variables, the Koyck lag estimate captures the stretch of time taken to acquire the median lag (Gujarati, 2004). The medial lag thus estimated is as shown below.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Koyck Median Lag} &= \frac{\log 2}{\log \lambda} \\
 \text{Rate of decay} &= \lambda \\
 \text{Speed of Adjustment} &= 1 - \lambda = 0.304141
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore;

$$\lambda = 1 - 0.304141 = 0.695859$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Koyck Median Lag} &= \frac{\log 2}{\log 0.695859} \\
 &= - \frac{0.3010}{0.1575} \\
 &= - 1.91 \\
 &= 1.91 \text{ (absolute)} \\
 &= 1.91 \times 12 \text{ months} \\
 &= 22.92 \text{ months}
 \end{aligned}$$

As lending rate and other adopted independent variables change, the first half or 50% of the total change in total domestic investment in the country is realized or accomplished at almost two times of the period, precisely 1 year and about 11 months. Total or 100% change in domestic investment will therefore be realized in about 3 years and 8 months.

The classical theory's inverse lending rate-investment link hypothesis which suggested that high rates tends to curb capital demand, is empirically supported by the negative coefficient (-0.010185) for lagged lending rates, indicating a dampened investment growth in Nigeria. The Keynesian theory hypothesis that lower rates boost investment through reduced liquidity preference is also established by the positive lagged investment effect (0.422421). The effect shows that past investments significantly propel current growth by 42%, although with a mild positive inflation impact (0.002908). The Duesenberry's theory hypothesis of interest rates causing cost escalation thus limiting access to fund, is evident in the derived error correction term (-0.304141). The ECT's 3.4% annual disequilibrium adjustment implies slow recovery from rate hikes, with Koyck median lag estimating 1.91 years for half-effect realization and about 4 years for full adjustment. This underscores the delayed but persistent negative rate impacts posed to investment amid the interplay between income and profit.

4.3.5 Structural Break

The study conducted a structural break check in the series to ascertain any likely external shocks, policy shifts or economic crises that may influence the employed series. The result is presented below

Table 6: Chow Test Result for Structural Break

F-statistics	1.901810	Prob.F(6,29)	0.1144
Log likelihood ratio	13.60391	Prob.Chi-Square(6)	0.0344
Wald Statistics	11.41086	Prob.Chi-Square(6)	0.0765

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025

The result of the Chow breakpoint test presented in Table 6 above yields mixed evidence. On the one hand, the F-statistic at 1.9018 with a p-value of 0.114 and Wald statistic of 11.4109 with p-value of 0.077 failed to reject the null hypothesis of no structural break at 5% level of significance. These suggest parameter stability across the study period. However, on the other hand, the log likelihood ratio of 13.6039 with a p-value of 0.034 rejects the null and signals the presence of structural break. This is as also noted by Belonwu and Amali, (2023). The mixed result suggests that in spite of certain existing stability observed between lending rates and investment growth in the country, there is a potential for shift in the relationship, as may be caused by economic issues such as domestic policy changes or global financial influences.

4.3.6 Diagnostic Tests

The estimated parameters in the study results were subjected to Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation test and the heteroskedasticity test. While the serial correlation test checks for autocorrelation in the errors of the estimated parameters in the regression model, the heteroskedasticity test ascertains whether the variance of errors from the model's output does not correlate with the values of the independent variables

Table 7: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test Result

<i>Statistics</i>	<i>Values</i>
F-statistics	2.1598
Prob. F (4,26)	0.1018
Obs*R ²	9.9761
Prob. Chi-Squared(2)	0.0408

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025

Table 6 above presents results of the serial correlation test. The F-statistics is 2.1598 with corresponding p-value of 0.1018 which is not significant at any statistically accepted threshold. The null hypothesis of no serial correlation cannot be rejected.

Table 8: Heteroskedasticity Test Result

F-statistics	0.770819	Prob. F(9,30)	0.6438
Obs*R ²	7.512581	Prob. Chi-Squared (9)	0.5839
Scaled explained SS	14.05551	Prob. Chi-Squared (9)	0.1204

Source: Authors' Computation, 2025

In the heteroskedasticity test result table above, the estimated F-statistic has a value of 0.770819 with corresponding p-value of 0.6438 (64.38%) which is statistically insignificant. The study, therefore, cannot reject the null hypothesis of no heteroskedasticity.

5. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The attributable low total domestic investment to high lending rate in Nigeria kept output level and by extension income level, low. This is because high lending rate drains return on investment because investors' production efforts only ends up in the purse of lenders. The empirical findings established that a 1 percentage point increase in the previous year's lending rate is associated with a 1.02% reduction in current total domestic investment. This is a pointer to substantial economic drawback; for instance, with the sample average total domestics investment of N11,032 billion, the 1.02% reduction translates to an approximate N112 billion decrease. This is an indication that Nigeria's growth challenges may potentially be exacerbated. The negative influence of lending rate on total domestic investment in Nigeria had also been previously discovered to be a bane on investment growth (Apere and Akarara, 2024; Inimino, *et al.*, 2018).

However, in contrast to the establishment of this study, interest rate at which capital is released to investors was noted to positively affect domestic investment in the long run rather than in the short-run, through multiplier effects that exist among macroeconomic variables (Nwamuo and Agu, 2022). When both sides of the findings are jointly consideration, it is still clear that the immediate negative effect of high lending rate and the possible long-run positive effect, which is undefined, retrogresses investment. As found in the research, the growth of domestic investment level being influenced by previous investment holds true and explains the basis for economic expansion. This confirms the positions of Iortyer and Onuh, (2022) and Ijirshar, *et al.* (2019) where the influence of domestic investment was found to propel growth in Nigeria and other countries in Africa. Exchange rate did not emanate significant impact on total

domestic investment. It is an indication that while its relevance as major macroeconomic variable is important, lending rate and past investments have stronger hold on current and future level of domestic investment in Nigeria (Apere and Akarara, 2024; Ijirshar, *et al.* 2019; Inimino, *et al.*, 2018). However, inflation rate has a negative but mild influence on the growth of total domestic investment. This corroborates the findings of Taiga and Adofu, (2021) and Iheonu and Nwakeze, (2016).

Since it has been established that it requires the country about 4 years to realize the full effect of any adjustment made on its domestic investment, lending rate and other variables, while their individual direction of effects have been known, suffice that a guide as to which variable to adjust and in what direction, is provided. The 30.4% annual adjustment speed and median lag of 1.91 years for half the effect, with full realization in about four years, provides a window for the country's Monetary Policy Rate, to adopt targeted measures towards real sectors, while implementing macro-prudential tools like reduced cash reserve ratios for banks channeling credit to SMEs.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study examined domestic investment growth response to lending rate in Nigeria over a period of 42 year, between 1981 and 2023. Lending rate adversely affects the growth of total domestic investment in the country while past total domestic investment leads to more growth in domestic investment. Inflation and exchange rates never had appreciable influence on the growth of total domestic investment.

The study thus recommends as follows;

- i. The CBN needs to establish a targeted interest rate corridor to cap prime lending rates at 15-18%, while balancing inflation control with investment growth. The adjustments dynamics identified in the study should be monitored over the 4-year realization timeline.
- ii. Implementation of macro-prudential measures, such as cash reserve ratios reduction, for banks that direct huge loans to real sectors. This helps to counter the dampening effect of high lending rates on domestic investment.
- iii. Real-time tracking of domestic investment responses through the Central bank's monitoring of lending rates, inflation and credit flows. This will enable proactive response or adjustments to disequilibria at the annual speed noted in the study.

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